

Evaluating the repeatability of myocardial T1 mapping using Open-MOLLI at 3T

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Summary:

Standardization of T1 mapping using vendor-neutral techniques provides robust measurements and is likely to facilitate wider clinical adoption. The open-source myocardial T1 mapping (Open-MOLLI) was applied in 3.0T. Results show similar repeatability in vivo between MOLLI and Open-MOLLI.

Introduction:

Standardization of T1 mapping allows greater confidence in cross-site comparisons [1], but it can be difficult with vendor-specific products due to differences in estimation that are not easy to remove. Meanwhile, a vendor-neutral sequence methodology may reduce sequence variations [2] and facilitate wider clinical adoption of cardiac T1 mapping. The open-source framework Pulseseq[3] has been used to successfully execute the same pulse sequence on different scanners[4]. With the same aim, we previously developed the open-source myocardial T1 mapping (Open-MOLLI)[5] as a baseline sequence for testing further sequence improvements, while facilitating inter-scanner and cross-vendor reproducibility studies. This sequence was initially studied at 1.5T. The aim of this study was to evaluate the repeatability of the estimated T1 maps at 3.0T, comparing it with those obtained using the vendor-supplied MOLLI implementation.

Methods:

Open-MOLLI is an inversion-recovery sequence with balanced steady-state free precession imaging (bSSFP) readout with inversion and trigger scheme 5(3)3 (i.e. two inversions the first with 5 and the second with 3 T1-weighted images) similar to MOLLI. It is available at <https://github.com/asgaspar/OpenMOLLI>.

Open-MOLLI and MOLLI were acquired in 12 healthy subjects (36±12 y) using at 3.0T Siemens PrismaFit Scanner with 32-channel body coil. For 6 volunteers, both sequences were repeated in each session to study repeatability.

The acquisition parameters are presented in Table 1. For Open-MOLLI, the field-of-view (FOV) was $354 \times 327 \text{ mm}^2$. For MOLLI, FOV was $354 \times 302 \text{ mm}^2$, and partial Fourier (PF) was applied in both directions (acquired matrix 202×124 which corresponds to PF of 86% in the phase direction and 79% in the readout direction). The initial and shortest inversion time (TI) was 171 ms for Open-MOLLI and 100 ms for MOLLI.

Data were exported and reconstructed offline in Matlab using GRAPPA, and adaptive coil combination to obtain Phase Sensitive Inversion Recovery signals that were used for T1 estimation. T1 estimation was performed using 3-parameter analytic model $\text{Signal}(A,B,T1^*)=A-B \cdot \exp(-TI/T1^*)$ with correction of $T1=(B/A-1)T1^*$ [6]. Manual segmentation of the myocardium was performed, along with segmental analysis according to the AHA 16-segment model [7].

The accuracy of Open-MOLLI T1 estimates was evaluated by considering MOLLI T1 values as the reference in a Bland–Altman analysis. A paired, two-sided Wilcoxon signed-rank test was performed to compare MOLLI and Open-MOLLI methods. The within-subject coefficient of variation (CV_w) for the T1 values was estimated in each cardiac segment given by the ratio of the within-subject standard deviation (SD) to its mean value. The repeatability coefficient (RC) is given in percentage from $\text{RC}(\%)=2.77\text{CV}_w$.

Results:

MOLLI and Open-MOLLI sequences were acquired in 12 subjects, but due to artifacts related to heart motion, one subject was excluded. It was not possible to acquire three slices in another subject who was thus not included in the segmental analysis. Figure 1A shows the T1-weighted images obtained for the first TI obtained with MOLLI and Open-MOLLI for one representative subject. T1 maps for the same subject are also presented in Figure 1B.

Mean myocardial T1 over all slices was $T1^{\text{MOLLI}}=1154 \pm 23 \text{ ms}$ vs $T1^{\text{Open-MOLLI}}=1129 \pm 43 \text{ ms}$. The mean T1 difference between Open-MOLLI and MOLLI was 22 ms (p-value=0.03) with a confidence interval of [-78, 33] ms (see Figure 2B and 2C). The segmental distribution of the mean T1 estimate according with AHA 16-segments model is presented in Figure 2A. The SD of within-segment T1 estimate is also presented in Figure 2A, where it is possible to observe higher SD across all segments for Open-MOLLI.

Within session test-retest of MOLLI and Open-MOLLI was performed on 6 subjects, but as stated before one had to be excluded. No statistical differences were found between the T1 estimates between the two repetitions with either sequence (Fig. 3); the mean difference of T1 values between scan 1 and 2 for MOLLI and Open-MOLLI were $\Delta T1^{\text{MOLLI}}=0.13 \text{ ms}$ (p-value=0.95) and $\Delta T1^{\text{Open-MOLLI}}=2.7 \text{ ms}$ (p-value=0.40). The confidence interval (1.96 SD) of the mean difference for MOLLI was [-9.3, 9.0] ms, while for Open-MOLLI it was [-9.8, 15] ms. The RC within-subject was 0.37% for MOLLI and 0.54% for Open-MOLLI.

Discussion & Conclusions:

Open-MOLLI and MOLLI presented a mean bias of -22 ms. Although further tests are needed to evaluate Open-MOLLI's clinical performance but these are promising results towards increasing accessibility to myocardial T1 mapping via Open-MOLLI.

The repeatability of both sequences was similar and higher than described at 1.5T ($RC^{MOLLI}=3.0\%;RC^{Open-MOLLI}4.4\%$)[5], possibly due to improvement in signal-to-noise ratio at 3.0T.

This work shows that the repeatability of MOLLI and Open-MOLLI are similar at 3.0T. With the implementation of Open-MOLLI in a different center, we show that this sequence can be easily applied in inter-scanner reproducibility studies.

References:

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Images

Table 1: Acquisition parameters for in vivo acquisitions with MOLLI and Open-MOLLI sequences.

	MOLLI	Open-MOLLI
FOV (mm ²)	354×302	354×327
TR/TE (ms)	2.24/1.12	3.04/1.52
Slice Thickness (mm)	8	
FA (°)	35	
Matrix	256×144	
Reconstructed Matrix	265×218	
BW (Hz/pixel)	1085	808
Partial Fourier (%)	86	-
Minimum TI (ms)	100	171

Figure 1: (A) T1-weighted images obtained with MOLLI and Open-MOLLI in a healthy subject. inversion times (TI) for each image are presented on the right, and respective (B) T1 maps (in ms) for both sequences.

Figure 2: (A) Segmental distribution of T1 values over 10 healthy subjects (B) Correlation between MOLLI and Open-MOLLI; (C) Bland–Altman analysis comparing T1 values obtained with Open-MOLLI and MOLLI.

Figure 3: Repeatability of MOLLI (blue) and Open-MOLLI (red), over 5 healthy subjects: (A) Correlation with Pearson correlation coefficient squared (r^2); (B) Bland–Altman analysis for T1 values comparing between scan repetitions. Repeatability coefficients (RC) for MOLLI and Open-MOLLI are presented. Results show that repeatability is similar between MOLLI and Open-MOLLI.